
Ownership Patterns in Shaping Management Practices of Private Radio Stations in Nigeria

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Abstract

The deregulation of the broadcast sector in 1992 has influenced the ownership structures in radio ownership patterns in Nigeria. These structures emerged in the form of political, religious, corporate and individual, thereby shaping radio's operation and content delivery. This study explored the relationship between ownership patterns and the management practices employed by private radio stations in Nigeria. Using the political economy media theory and agency theory, the conceptual study posited that the nature of ownership, whether individual, corporate, religious or politically affiliated, significantly influences operational strategies, programming decisions, financial management. The researchers further observed that ownership influences not only operational efficiency, but also the ideological orientation of media output, impact station autonomy, revenue generation strategies, adherence to professional journalism standards and affects public trust and journalistic independence.

Keywords: Ownership Patterns, Management Practices, Media Management, Organisational Culture, Editorial Independence, Private Radio Stations, Nigeria

Introduction

Historically, media ownership in many parts of the world is private and non-corporate (Sjovaag, 2019). This can be attributed to why the Nigerian media space has experienced a lot of growth with broadcast media, including private radio stations, assuming an important role in recent times. The concept of media deregulation in Nigeria emerged in 1992 with the deregulation of the broadcast industry (Ojebode & Adegbola, 2019). The General Ibrahim Babangida's administration succeeded in deregulating the broadcast landscape with the enactment of Decree 38 of 1992. This ushered in the establishment of private broadcast stations nationwide. The National Broadcasting Commission (NBC) was then established, tasked with overseeing broadcasting in the nation. Before his administration ended, Babangida made sure that private radio and television licenses were granted. To that administration's credit, a large number of private television and radio stations received licenses and started up.

Oketunmbi (2007) claimed that wider programming freedom is one of the most evident outcomes of deregulation and the growth of broadcasting stations in Nigeria. Programming, according to broadcasting terminology, is the process of choosing and

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planning what will be broadcast; it deals with the questions of what will air, when, and for how long. Unquestionably, the 1992 deregulation of the broadcast sector changed the media landscape in Nigeria and allowed for more active communication between media professionals.

The media landscape in Nigeria has undergone a significant transformation with the deregulation of the broadcast sector, leading to a substantial increase in the number of privately owned radio stations (Nigerian Communications Commission, 2023). These private radio stations play a vital role in disseminating information, shaping public discourse and contributing to the socio-economic development of the nation. The array of ownership structures and conceptual basis sustaining these stations gives rise to significant questions about the forms and modalities in which these stations operate. It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to assess the relationship between ownership patterns and the management practices employed by private radio stations in Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarification

Radio

Radio is a broadcast communication based on the spectrum which transmits electromagnetic wave signals to the people. As a mass medium, radio reaches millions of people in society. Radio is important in every society as spoken words, music and other communication signals are shared with the public through waves which are received at home by sets (Apuke, 2017). Radio broadcast features different segments such as sports, news, interviews, discussions and music among others. That is to say, radio signals can be transmitted to any part of the world. Radio stations are set up by the government, individuals or corporations. Government stations are owned and financed by the state, with the management team being constituted by the state. Private ownership, on the other hand, could be corporate-based, individual or group. Each of these entities decides on what to do with its outlet.

Furthermore, private radio ownership refers to the situation where personalities (one person or group of persons or institutions) found, fund and direct the management of the radio media business. Private radio stations are found in every part of Nigeria today. Some of the notable private radio stations are The Beats FM, Grace FM, Raypower FM, Rhythm FM, Cool FM, Platinum FM, among many others. In this regard, the individual or individuals or institution see to the success of the station in all ramifications.

Media Management

According to Omeonu & Chukwu-Okoronkwo (2020), there are numerous ways to interpret the term "management." It can be viewed as a procedure for carrying out particular tasks in order to manage a business. In other words, it is a process of achieving organisational goals by the combined efforts of people as well as other available resources (Omeonu & Chukwu-Okoronkwo, 2020). The fundamental idea is that management relates to people and is a process by which people carry out tasks, regardless of how the term is interpreted. Managers are those who direct organisational actions

toward the accomplishment of the purposes or objectives for which the organisation was founded and are collectively referred to as management.

Management is the process of accomplishing organisational objectives for ongoing operations in order to enhance performance through the combined efforts of individuals and other resources that are accessible in broadcast media organisations. Broadcast media management, according to Omeonu & Chukwu-Okoronkwo (2020), is the arrangement of all components of the broadcast industry such as personnel, buildings, equipment in a way that involves the process of getting the activities of the organisations through the employers and employees by creating and preserving a cooperative environment. This implies that to accomplish the goals and objectives of the organisation, component units must cooperate. To accomplish their goals, broadcast organisations must have efficient and successful organisational structures.

Ownership and Media Management

The concept of media ownership can be described as the legal and economic control of media organisations by government or private bodies (Benson, 2025). According to Picard (2020), media ownership is a critical factor in shaping organisational behaviour. For instance, private radio stations in Nigeria are often influenced by the economic and political interests of their proprietors (Adeyemi & Popoola, 2022). This is evident as stations owned by politicians may prioritise partisan content, while those under religious ownership may emphasise faith-based programming. Each owner decides what content and programmes it will use for its operations.

Every government or private body that establishes a media outlet must always have control over the management structures, including editorial and content. Therefore, Rauf in Owolabi & Akanni (2020, p. 97) also refers to media ownership as “the authority of an individual over a media outfit.” There are seven forms of media ownership, namely: international corporations, national corporations, small-scale organisations, government, community, individual and non-profit (Warren, 2007 in Owolabi&Akanni, 2020). But the most common forms of ownership are government and private. Aside from the government-owned media, all the other forms of classification by the author can be merged into privately owned.

On this note, Albaran (2017) posits that management practices in media organisations encompass strategic decision-making, resource allocation and audience engagement. Nweze *et al* (2019, p.104) describe such a type of management practice as “he who pays the piper dictates the tune.” In Nigeria, private radio stations face challenges such as funding constraints, regulatory pressures, and competition, which ownership structures either exacerbate or mitigate (Nwabueze & Okonkwo, 2023).

Review of Literature

There are few studies on the country's private radio stations' growth rate, but there are a few on radio issues and their contributions to rural, community, and national development (Oder, 2016; Bernice *et al* 2020). According to Ogbu & Onekutu (2018), a workable framework must be created and established in order to run and maintain a radio

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station in Nigeria. Similarly, there are a couple of studies that were done on the operational management of radio broadcasting around the globe, in Africa and Nigeria in particular. However, most of these studies were interested in investigating management frameworks for public broadcast radio stations (Godson-Amamoo, 2017; Omeonu & Chukwu-Okoronkwo, 2020). It is few studies that interrogate private broadcasting (Amos & Joseph, 2023).

McQuail 2010 stresses the need for editorial independence, content diversity, and openness in media ownership and management techniques. Different ownership structures, such as family-owned, corporate or government-affiliated (Doyle, 2002), may affect the management approaches and material creation process. A range of ownership models, including private citizens, corporations, and government-affiliated organisations, characterise the Nigerian media landscape. Liberation of Nigeria's broadcast sector in the 1990s produced a proliferation of independently owned radio stations, each with distinct editorial approaches and managerial systems. The ownership structure, which can include sole proprietorships, family businesses, corporate conglomerates, and political affiliates, frequently causes these variances. Less studies have methodologically examined how ownership affects internal management policies, although scholarly interest has concentrated on the consequences of ownership on content (Oso, 2012).

Ownership control on the behaviour and mode of operations of various media organisations is common in almost all industrial sectors (Aguilera & Crespi-Cladera, 2012; Jensen & Meckling, 1976). In the mass media industry, the types of content, journalistic and human resource structures and target goals of the organisation have been opined to have been significantly controlled by their ownership structures (Baker, 2007; Doyle, 2002). The Nigerian private radio stations' structures and mode of operation, and sustainability are largely determined by the type of ownership (Owolabi & Akanni, 2020). While radio stations owned by the state pursue and reflect the government's agenda and interests, privately owned stations, on the other hand, reflect the laid-down structures and purpose behind their establishment. For example, an owner could set up his radio station for political reasons. Hence, these diverse ownership models, according to Umejei (2021), include religious organisations, individual ownerships, corporate entities, institutions and politically affiliated investors; each determining diverse management practices.

Overview of Ownership of Private Radio in Nigeria

The Nigerian private radio landscape exhibits a diverse range of ownership patterns, which include individual/entrepreneurial, corporate, religious, politically affiliated and community ownership. Individual and entrepreneurial ownership entails stations owned by single individuals, often entrepreneurs or media veterans. These are private individuals or groups with business interests. Their management practices might reflect the owner's personal vision, values, and management style, potentially leading to more centralised decision-making and a strong emphasis on the owner's priorities. Many private radio stations in Nigeria, such as Inspiration FM and Cool FM, are spearheaded by individual entrepreneurs. These stations typically adopt flexible, profit-driven

management styles. Decision-making is centralised, often in the hands of the owner, leading to informal and personality-driven administrative processes (Ojebode, 2013).

Some radio stations are owned by media conglomerates or diversified business entities in the form of corporate ownership. These are media companies or conglomerates owning multiple outlets. These stations might adopt more formalised and standardised management practices, driven by corporate policies, performance targets, and a focus on profitability and market share. Corporate radio stations such as Nigeria Info and others under media conglomerates demonstrate more formalised structures. These organisations employ strategic management principles, performance metrics, and diversified revenue models. However, the corporate goal of profitability may sometimes compromise journalistic integrity (Ogundimu, 2007).

There are radio stations owned by religious organisations, either Christian or Muslim. It is common to see churches or religious bodies managing stations for faith-based programming. Their management practices are often guided by religious doctrines, ethical principles, and a mission to propagate their faith and values. Programming content and operational guidelines are likely to be heavily influenced by the religious tenets of the owning organisation. Furthermore, some stations are owned by individuals or entities with strong political connections or affiliations. That is, politicians owning stations to advance political agendas. These stations might exhibit management practices geared towards promoting the political interests of their owners, potentially influencing news coverage, programme selection and the overall editorial stance. Radio stations like RayPower FM, originally linked with politically exposed persons, often reflect the ideological leanings of their sponsors. These outlets exhibit low editorial independence, with programming tailored to suit political objectives. Staff appointments may reflect loyalty rather than competence, undermining professional standards (Uche, 1989). Although, less prevalent in the commercial sector, a few stations may operate under community-based ownership models, where management is driven by the needs and interests of a specific geographic or social community. Each ownership model exerts influence over editorial freedom, recruitment practices, funding mechanisms, and operational transparency.

Review of Empirical Studies

There are various studies which have tried to critically evaluate ownership patterns and media management in Nigeria and globally. These research works were tailored towards areas that explain how ownership patterns enhance editorial policies, human resources and the independence of media and radio broadcasting in Nigeria. Consequently, Amos & Joseph (2023) conducted a critical evaluation of Nigerian private media organisations to understand ownership and news coverage. By relying on secondary data, the conceptual study entitled “media ownership and news coverage: a critical appraisal of private media organisations” argued that ownership of media has different characteristics depending on whether and when it is politically exciting or economically beneficial.

Amos & Joseph further projected that when news production is a profitable investment, corporate owners who want to increase their profits on the public stock

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market are usually drawn to it. Hence, the study concluded that news production usually attracts industry, military, or partisan ownership when investments are politically advantageous. The present and former studies are similar as both appraised the media ownership's influence in Nigeria. The studies are dissimilar in the areas of scope, with the present study focusing on private radio ownership while the former work was on general media ownership and news coverage in Nigeria.

Fatonji *et al* (2023) conducted a study on the impact of media ownership structures on editorial independence and news reporting in the digital age and found that ownership affects editorial independence in every media, including digital new media. The study, which used a qualitative interview method to interview digital media journalists, also discovered that journalists, including radio practitioners, sometimes deviate from professionalism due to the pressure that comes from ownership's interests and their job security. The authors concluded that ownership influence is sacrosanct in every newsroom operation, regardless of the media type. However, among its recommendations is that media owners should create an enabling environment to safeguard the independence of their stations. The relationship between this study and the present paper stems from the fact that both works tried to acknowledge the role of media owners in the management practices of media stations. On the other hand, their differences lie in the fact that both studies are dissimilar in methodology and time. In addition, Fatonji *et al's* study evaluates digital media challenges, while the present study focuses on private radio management structures.

In another conceptual study on "broadcast management in Nigeria, Iredia (2015) assesses multiple media management systems to find the most suitable ones for controlling broadcasting in developing countries such as Nigeria. The select methods are then examined to highlight their advantages so that any broadcast manager can easily adopt them. In the process, the study found and concluded that while it is simple to adopt some management strategies used by many successful broadcast stations, such as effective leadership, good hiring and training practices, and overall quality management, it is more difficult to imitate how others have handled or are handling the critical aspects of their organisation's environment because every environment has unique characteristics.

The relationship between the present study and Iredia's work is, both are conceptual as they rely on secondary data for their analysis. The differences between both studies rest on the dimensions and research approaches, with the present study focusing mainly on private radio in Nigeria, while the former analysed the system approach as an imperative for broadcast management in Nigeria.

Furthermore, a qualitative study by Ugwu (2018) on the "influence of radio ownership on professional practice revealed that radio owners have significant influence on the professionalism of their stations, such as in the case of newsroom operations. Using content reviews and interviews, the author maintains that some stations restrict freedom of the press to suit the objectives of their owners. Hence, the study concluded that ownership is powerful in every radio operation as it hinders and supports professionalism in journalism, depending on the values of the owners. Therefore, Ugwu recommended that radio stations should create distinctions clearly stating editorial boundaries and that more training on media ethics and professionalism should be provided for the staff. Both studies are conceptual and explore the effects of ownership on editorial practice and the integrity of journalists, while their differences lie in the fact

that the present study is concerned with how ownership patterns shape management practices in private radio in Nigeria, the former study focuses on newsroom operations.

Betianga's (2013) article was a conceptual paper on policies and management of broadcast media in Nigeria within the last 50 years. The study's conclusions were based on a critical and interpretive reading of Nigerian television's history, form, and content, starting with Obafemi Awolowo's Western Nigeria Television in Ibadan and continuing through the Nigeria Television Authority, the federal government's reactive national network, and eventually states and private television stations. Similarly, Godson Amamoo's 2017 study also examines the management interdependence between publicly backed and privately sponsored media businesses. Many studies supported the assertions that the two groups had divergent aims and beliefs. While for-profit companies centre on operational efficiency, nonprofit groups place more emphasis on issues related to human development. By providing stakeholders with better program options, the study provides broadcasting companies with information on maximising their assets and promoting positive social transformation in community development.

Summarily, the reviewed studies and the present study share some similarities and differences. The present studies and the previous ones are similar in the sense that all studies tried to evaluate the central role of media owners in shaping media and radio operations and the effects of ownership on journalistic practice and professionalism.

Theoretical Framework

Several theoretical lenses can inform our understanding of how ownership patterns shape management practices. However, this study underpinned the political economy of media theory and agency theory in understanding how ownership patterns shape management practices of private radio operations.

Political Economy Media Theory

Developed by McChesney (2004) and Mosco (2009), this theory is concerned with how economic interests, as well as ownership structures and power relations, influence media operations, content and other forms of organisational behaviour. The theory postulates that ownership and control determine the priorities of media organisations. The interconnections among politics, economics and the media are scrutinised by this theory. In describing how media ownership shapes management processes, the theory further analyses how power structures, economic systems, and political ideologies communicate and impact media institutions, practices, and content. With historical context to the ideas of Karl Max, Antonio Gramsci & Adam Smith, media institutions, according to this theory, function within the limitations of political and economic structures that influence governance, content and labour relations (Mosco, 2009).

Agency Theory

This theory suggests that conflicts of interest may develop between principals (owners) and agents (managers) when their goals and objectives are not aligned (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Different ownership structures may lead to varying principal-agent relationships and consequently influence managerial decision-making to align with the

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owners' objectives (Schein, 2010). For example, family-owned stations might prioritise long-term sustainability and family interests over short-term profit maximisation, potentially leading to different investment and operational strategies compared to publicly traded media conglomerates. When it comes to private radio stations, the theory postulates that managers are essentially driven to operate in the best interests of the organisation and its stakeholders, particularly when there is a strong sense of identification and trust. Ownership structures that foster closer relationships between owners and managers, such as smaller, privately held entities, might see management practices driven by a sense of stewardship and commitment to the owners' vision. In this sense, editorial independence will be minimal as programme production and the station operation will be guided by the owners' editorial guidelines.

Both theories offer explanations on how ownership patterns influence management practices in private radio operations; while political economy theory focuses on how ownership structures influence the media system, the Agency theory explains the internal organisational dynamics that exist between media owners and their managers. Both theories are relevant to this study because they create room to understand the impact of ownership matters in the day-to-day management of private radio stations in Nigeria.

Methodology

This study is conceptual; hence, to arrive at its conclusions, various literature involving published and unpublished manuscripts was consulted to understand how ownership patterns shape management practices in private radio stations in Nigeria.

Discussion

Ownership influence is sacrosanct in the management practice of radio stations in Nigeria because as it is found in other places, most media owners established their stations with aims and objectives. The private radio owners shape the programme orientation, editorial policy, human resource management, professionalism ethics and day-to-day operational structure of the station. Therefore, there are other visible ownership patterns that exert significant influence on various aspects of management practices in Nigerian private radio stations.

In the aspect of programming and content strategy, the owners' objectives and values dictate the type of content broadcast, the target audience, and the overall programming philosophy. For instance, religiously owned stations will always prioritise religious content, while politically affiliated stations might focus on political discourse and propaganda. Likewise, corporate owners will likely emphasise content that attracts a large audience and generates advertising revenue for the radio station.

In terms of organisational and operational control, ownership patterns still determine managerial appointments, resource allocation, and strategic direction. Private owners typically exercise strong operational control, including hiring key staff aligned with their vision, which affects station performance and public trust (Amos & Joseph, 2023). This control enhances efficiency but may also limit journalistic independence. The managerial dependencies between privately and publicly supported media organisations

are examined in Godson-Amamoo's (2017) study. The assertions that the two organisations function according to distinct principles and ideals were validated by a number of tests. Organisations that are not profit-driven tend to focus on enhancing issues of development and growth, while profit-based organisations prioritise efficient and effective operations. The paper offers private radio stations' perceptions and insights into enhanced programme development and community transformation through commendable programme alternatives for media stakeholders.

Therefore, in the area of financial management, the type of media ownership to a large extent still controls the financial influence, capacity and decision-making process of the Radio Station, which includes measures of cost control, revenue generation models and investment strategies. Individual ownership patterns might be funded by a more personal financial management, while corporate ownership might focus on efficiency and profit-making. Private radio stations with political affiliations might benefit from political alliances and patronage in boosting their revenue drive.

For human resource management, ownership patterns also determine the practices and implementation of the organisation's culture and policies. This is because it has control over staff recruitment, human resources and employee relationships, staff training and benefit plans. Stations owned by families give precedence to personal relationships and loyalty, while corporate organisations most likely focus on human resource management procedures. More so, ownership structures have a great impact on the radio station's branding and marketing strategies. Stations that operate under corporate entities might invest in elaborate campaigns to enhance their brand. On the other hand, individually owned stations rely on door-to-door and local connections in building their audience base. Stations owned by religious organisations focus on faith-based content and ideologies with which their target audience can relate and identify.

In terms of editorial independence and journalistic standards, journalists may have different levels of media autonomy largely based on the impact of the ownership structure of the radio stations. Ownership can affect the editorial and Journalistic level of Professional freedom. Politically affiliated owners might exert pressure on news coverage, while religiously owned stations might have specific guidelines on the portrayal of certain issues. Owners exert significant influence over editorial policies and programming content, often aligning broadcasts with their interests. This can lead to biased news coverage favouring owners' political or economic objectives, compromising journalistic objectivity (Amos & Joseph, 2023). For example, stations like Splash FM, Ibadan, have been studied for ownership influence on news objectivity, revealing constraints on editorial freedom due to ownership pressures. Findings revealed that stations owned by political figures often exhibit bias in news reporting, while corporate-owned stations maintain relatively balanced coverage due to commercial interests in audience retention. Research on media ownership and management practices highlights the importance of editorial independence, content diversity, and transparency (McQuail, 2010). Different ownership structures, such as family-owned, corporate or government-affiliated, can influence management practices and content production (Doyle, 2002). In

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Nigeria, the media landscape is characterised by diverse ownership patterns, including private individuals, corporate entities, and government-affiliated organisations.

For regulatory compliance and external relations, ownership might influence how stations navigate regulatory requirements and interact with government agencies and other external stakeholders. Politically connected owners have an advantage in dealing with regulatory bodies. The deregulation of Nigeria's broadcasting sector in 1992 under General Babangida's regime allowed private ownership to flourish, creating a competitive media environment (Amos & Joseph, 2023). Despite this, government policies and legal frameworks continue to impact management practices, with government interference occasionally limiting editorial independence, especially in government-owned stations.

Conclusion

This conceptual paper has argued that ownership patterns play an essential part in influencing the management practices of private radio stations in Nigeria. By drawing on relevant theories and considering the unique context of the Nigerian media landscape, it has highlighted the potential influence of individual, corporate, religious, and political ownership on various aspects of station operations. Ownership is a critical determinant of management practices in private radio stations in Nigeria. The ownership patterns of private radio stations are governed by ideology, profit or influence, which significantly controls their management, content, professionalism, human resources and accountability. Understanding these differences is significant in developing a professionally independent and sustainable private radio sector in Nigeria. The connection between management and media ownership models buttresses the importance of a detailed understanding and perspective for development and agenda setting.

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